

1,3,5-TRIARIL 2-PIRAZOLINAS COM SUBSTITUINTE 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINIC: SÍNTESE, FOTOFÍSICO PROPERTIES E ATIVIDADE BIOLÓGICA

1,3,5-TRIARYL 2-PYRAZOLINES WITH 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINIC SUBSTITUENT: SYNTHESSES, PHOTOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES, AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

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RESUMO

Background. 1,3,5-triaril-2-pirazolinas são luminóforos orgânicos com Arylic radicais que mostram uma ampla atividade biológica e são usadas como cintiladores líquidos e materiais electro-ópticos. **Experimental.** Onze 2-pirazolinas foram sintetizados a partir phenylhidrazine e chalconas da série 8-hidroxiquinolina: 3- (5-il-8-hidroxiquinolina) -1- (3-R) -phenylprop-2-enona e 1- (8-hydroxyquinolin- 5-il) -3 - (3-R) -phenylprop-2-enona, em que R = H, CH₃, OCH₃, N (CH₃)₂, Cl, Br, e NO₂. As estruturas foram confirmadas por análise elementar, IV, ¹H-RMN e espectroscopia electrónica. **Resultados e discussão.** Os substituintes 1 e 3 arilo do anel pirazolino produzido turnos para comprimentos de onda mais curtos ou mais longos, em absorção e fluorescência. O fragmento hydroxyquinolinic receptor de elétrons influenciado o espectro de absorção e luminescência; a eventual causa dos baixos rendimentos quânticos de pirazolinas **4a-g** (1-fenil-3- (4-R-fenil) -5- (8-hydroxyquinolinil-5) -2-pirazolina) pode ser a extinção da fluorescência intramolecular específica em sistemas bicromophores, característica de pyrazolina 5-aceitador substituídos, e, em série **5a-g** (1-fenil-5- (4-R-fenil) -3- (8 hydroxyquinolinil-5)-2-pirazolina) no reacções transferência de protões intramolecular do estado animado (ESIPT), e aumentar dador-aceitador interação intramolecular de as suas moléculas excitadas. Cálculos funcionais da Densidade (método PM6) foram usadas para sondar a estrutura e energia electrónicas encomendas do emissiva e os estados de transferência de electrões e concordou com os dados experimentais. 1-fenil-3- (4-R-fenil) -5- (8-hydroxyquinolinil-5) -2-pirazolina mostrou actividade fungistática e fungicidas. Além disso, todas as pirazolinas mostraram largas actividades biológicas teóricos.

Palavras-chave: 1,3,5-triari 2-pirazolinas; 8-hidroxiquinolina; chalcones; Reações ESIPT; fluorescência; actividade biológica; actividade fungistática; actividade fungicida

ABSTRACT

Background. 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines are organic luminophores with aryl radicals that show a wide biological activity and are used as liquid scintillators and electro-optic materials. **Experimental.** Eleven 2-pyrazolines were synthesized from phenylhydrazine and chalcones of the 8-hydroxyquinoline series: 3-(8-hydroxyquinolin-5-yl)-1-(3-R)-phenylprop-2-enone and 1-(8-hydroxyquinolin-5-yl)-3-(3-R)-phenylprop-2-enone, where R = H, CH₃, OCH₃, N(CH₃)₂, Cl, Br, and NO₂. The structures were confirmed by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H-NMR, and electronic spectroscopy. **Results and discussion.** The 1- and 3- aryl substituents of the pyrazoline ring produced shifts to shorter or longer wavelengths, in absorbance and fluorescence. The electron acceptor hydroxyquinolinic fragment influenced the absorption and luminescence spectra; the possible cause of low quantum yields in pyrazolines **4a-g** (1-phenyl-3-(4-R phenyl)-5-(8-hydroxyquinolinil-5)-2-pyrazoline) may be

the specific intramolecular fluorescence quenching in bicromophores, characteristic of 5-acceptor substituted pyrazolines, and, in series **5a-g** (1-phenyl-5-(4-R phenyl)-3-(8-hydroxyquinolinil-5)-2-pyrazoline) of excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) reactions, and the increasing donor-acceptor intramolecular interaction of their excited molecules; Density functional calculations (method PM6) were used to probe the electronic structure and energy ordering of the emissive and the electron-transfer states; PM6 results agreed with the experimental data. 1-phenyl-3-(4-R phenyl)-5-(8-hydroxyquinolinil-5)-2-pyrazoline showed fungistatic and fungicide activities. Additionally, all our pyrazolines showed wide theoretical biological activities.

Keywords: 8-hydroxyquinoline; chalcones; ESIPT reactions; fluorescence; fungistatic activity; fungicide activity

INTRODUCTION

Among the most important organic luminophores are 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines (Hasan *et al.*, 2011), molecules with aryl radicals and the 8-hydroxyquinolinil-5 group in position 3 or 5. These compounds are used as liquid scintillators for ^{14}C counting (Wiley *et al.*, 1958) and high efficiency electro-optic materials (Wu *et al.*, 2000), and efficient photoacids to activate fluorescence dyes (Palaska *et al.* 2001); additionally, there has been a growing interest due to their antitumor (Insuasty *et al.*, 2012), antifungal (Deng *et al.*, 2012; Shekarchi *et al.*, 2008), antibacterial (Shekarchi *et al.*, 2008), antiviral (Shahar *et al.*, 2009), anti-inflammatory and other types of biological activities (Kumar, 2009).

The synthesis of 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines is often carried out from chalcones. Fahrni *et al.* (2003) synthesized 1,3,5-Triaryl-2-pyrazoline fluorophores, characterized their structures by X-ray analysis, and studied their photophysical properties by steady-state absorption and emission spectroscopy and redox potentials; these high-quantum-yield, low-toxicity 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines rendered attractive as *in vivo* intracellular pH probes. Li *et al.* (2007) synthesized 1,3,5-triaryl pyrazoline derivatives by reaction of chalcones and 3-chloro-6-hydrazinylpyridazine; the structures were determined by IR, ^1H NMR, HRMS spectra, and X-ray diffraction. Shandala and Hamdy (2008) synthesized a series of 1,3,5-pyrazolines by condensation of substituted chalcones with phenyl hydrazine; the synthesis was studied under phase transfer catalysis and the structures were elucidated by physical and spectroscopic methods. Finally, Sunil *et al.* (2009) cyclocondensed chalcones to obtain 1,3,5-triarylpyrazolines whose structures were established by IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectrometry; these compounds were evaluated for their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory

activities.

These 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines are interesting because they have luminescent and biological properties, and a large conjugated system that includes a pyrazoline ring and aryl substituents in positions 1 and 3 of this ring. In the conjugated chain $-\text{N}^1-\text{N}^2=\text{C}^3-$ of the pyrazoline ring, N^1 and C^3 are electron donating and withdrawing atoms, respectively; the carbon atom at position 5 does not conjugate with this chain; therefore, changing the substituents attached to this carbon atom should have only a small effect on the photophysical properties of pyrazolines and changing the groups attached to the 1- or 3-carbon atoms, should change these properties (Zhang *et al.*, 2000). Nevertheless, there is also evidence that substitution in position 5 affected fluorescence (Krasovitskii *et al.*, 1988).

The aims of this work were: a) to synthesize a series of 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines and investigate b) their biological activities, c) the effects of substitution in positions 1, 3, and 5 on photoluminescence, and d) the electronic structure and energy ordering of the excited and electron-transfer states through density functional calculations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The synthesis of chalcones **2a-g** (3-(8-hydroxyquinolin-5-yl)-1-(3-R)-phenylprop-2-enone) and **3a-g** (1-(8-hydroxyquinolin-5-yl)-3-(3-R)-phenylprop-2-enone), where R = H, CH_3 , OCH_3 , $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$, Cl, Br, and NO_2 , has been described (Marrugo González *et al.*, 2012).

2.1 Instruments

All reagents were analytical grade. The monitoring of reactions was performed by thin layer chromatography on Silufol UV-254 plates, with acetic acid as eluent. ^1H NMR spectra of **4a-g** and **5a-g** (Figure 1) were obtained on a Varian Mercury VX-200 (200 MHz) instrument in DMSO-

d₆, with trimethylsilane internal standard. Nitrogen was determined by the Dumas method. IR spectra were obtained using KBr pellets on a Specord IR-75 spectrometer. UV-vis absorption spectra were obtained on a Hitachi U3210 spectrometer and fluorescence on a Hitachi F4010 at 10⁻⁵ - 10⁻⁴ moles/L concentrations in toluene and 1 cm cells at 20°C. Quantum yields of fluorescence were measured in a fluorescein solution in sodium carbonate/sodium hydrogen carbonate buffer at pH 9.93 (fluorescein quantum yield 85%) and quinine sulfate 0.1 M in 1.0 N H₂SO₄ (fluorescein quantum yield: 54.6%) as fluorescence standards. Melting temperatures were determined in glass capillaries.

Figure 1. Structures of **4a** and **5a** series. The pyrazolinic ring and conjugation in fragment a give these molecules rigidity and planarity for an effective fluorescence. ACD/3D viewer version 14.01 (ACD, 2008) was used to generate the structures in this paper. H (gray), C (light blue), N (dark blue), O (red).

2.2 Synthesis of 4a

A solution of 0.20 g (0.96 mmol) of chalcone **2a** (Scheme 1), 0.33 g (3.06 mmol) of diphenylhydrazine, 4.0 ml of methanol, and 0.1 ml of piperidine as catalyst were heated under reflux for 5 hours. The product was washed with hot water and filtered, and compound **4a** was

extracted with n-hexane in a Soxhlet apparatus. Analogously, **4b-e** and **5a-e** were obtained using chalcones **2b-e**, and **3a-e**, respectively; reaction times and yields are shown in Table 1.

2.3 Synthesis of 4f

A solution of 0.20 g (0.96 mmol) of chalcone **2f**, 0.33 g (3.1 mmol) of diphenylhydrazine, 4.0 ml of methanol, and 0.1 mL of piperidine were heated under reflux for 5 hours. The precipitate, **4f**, was washed with water and crystallized from methanol. Analogously, compounds **4g**, **5f**, and **5g** were obtained using chalcones **2g**, **3f**, and **3g**, respectively (Table 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines. Chalcones **2a-g** and **3a-g** were cyclocondensed with phenylhydrazine. R = H (**2a** and **3a**), CH₃ (**2b** and **3b**), OCH₃ (**2c** and **3c**), N(CH₃)₂ (**2d** and **3d**), Cl (**2e** and **3e**), Br (**2f** and **3f**), and NO₂ (**2g** and **3g**).

2.4 Antifungal evaluation

Microorganisms and media. For antifungal evaluation, we used standardized strains from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), Rockville, MD, USA, and CEREMIC (CCC), Centro de Referencia en Micología, Facultad de Ciencias Bioquímicas y Farmacéuticas, Suipacha 531-(2000)-Rosario, Argentina: *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* ATCC 9763, *Cryptococcus neoformans* ATCC 32264, *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 9170, *A. fumigatus* ATCC 26934, *A. niger* ATCC 9029, *Trichophyton rubrum* CCC 110, *T. mentagrophytes* ATCC 9972 and *M. gypseum* CCC 115 (CLSI, 2008).

Antifungal susceptibility testing.

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum fungicidal concentration (MFC) of each compound were determined by using broth microdilution techniques Pacciaroni *et al.*, 2008) according to the guidelines of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) for yeasts (M27-A3) (CLSI, 2008a) and for filamentous fungi (M 38-A2) (CLSI, 2008b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Scheme 2. Properties of the δ -conjugated system and proton Interactions. The π -conjugated system gives fragment **a** rigidity and planarity (above). Proton Interactions in the series **4a-g** and **5a-g** (below)

8-hydroxyquinoline and its derivatives have chelating (Daneshfar *et al.*, 2012) and fluorescent properties (Kong *et al.*, 2012). We have described the synthesis of chalcones **2a-g** and **3a-g** (Scheme 1) from the condensation of 5-acetyl- and 5-formyl-8-hydroxyquinoline with substituted benzaldehydes and benzophenones (Marrugo González *et al.*, 2012). Here, these chalcones were cyclocondensed with phenylhydrazine and the 2-pyrazolines of series **4a-g** and **5a-g** were obtained (Scheme 1 and Table 1); yields were low in many cases, possibly by formation of complexes with contaminant

metal ions; the latter can also explain that melting temperatures for our compounds were higher (Table 1) than those reported in the literature (Vinogradov and Elinson, 1979) because metal-ligand complexes have higher melting points than the pure ligands.

3.1 Structural Analysis by elemental analysis, IR, UV-vis, and NMR

The composition and structure of **4a-g** and **5a-g** were confirmed by elemental analysis, IR, ^1H NMR and electronic spectroscopy (Tables 1-3, and supplementary material). IR spectra obtained in KBr pellets show the band of medium intensity $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of the pyrazolonic group (in the $\pi 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region) and the broad OH band (in the $3350\text{-}3410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region). Pyrazolonic protons were identified (ABX system, Scheme 2) and the hydroxyquinolinic proton signals (Table 2) of **4a-g** and **5a-g** (2H to 7H, scheme 2) were equivalent to the ^1H -NMR signals of chalcones **2a-g** and **3a-g** from which they were synthesized (Marrugo González *et al.*, 2012) indicating that the hydroxyquinolinic fragment kept its integrity during the reaction. Chemical shifts, δ , of hydroxyquinolinic 4-H and pyrazolonic H_x proton signals of **4a-g** differ on average 1.20 and -0.62 ppm (except H_x proton in **4g** and **5g**), respectively, from those of their **5a-g** isomers, which may be used for identification; for example, in **4a** and **5a**, the 4-H protons have a difference of 1.25 ppm and the protons H_x a difference of -0.62 ppm. These values reflect the spatial location of both heterocycles; in **4a-g**, 4-H and H_x protons approach, but in their **5a-g** isomers they move away and the 4-H proton falls under the anisotropic influence of the nitrogen in position 2 of the $-\text{N}^1-\text{N}^2=\text{C}^3-$ fragment (Scheme 2). In **4a-g**, H_x protons are under the influence of the hydroxyquinolinic ring but in their **5a-g** isomers they are affected only by a benzene ring.

3.2 Structure and fluorescence

The spectral properties of 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazoline luminophores were mainly determined by the length of the δ -conjugated system, which connects the $>\text{N}=\text{N}=\text{C}<$ hydrazone fragment and the aryl radicals in positions 1 and 3 of the pyrazoline (fragment **a**, scheme 2). The saturated bridge of two carbon atoms of the pyrazolonic ring and conjugation of fragment **a** give the system rigidity and planarity (Figure 1) for an effective

fluorescence, with quantum yields up to 0.7 (Svechkarev *et al.*, 2008; Yaya *et al.*, 2000) mainly as a result of a decrease of the tetrahedral degree of the nitrogen atom in position 1 (Kimura *et al.*, 1977). Pyrazolines **4a-g** and **5a-g** have such characteristics and, as expected, have luminescent properties. Table 3 shows the wavelengths of excitation and fluorescence in toluene of our 1,3,5-triaryl-2-pyrazolines.

The Stokes shifts ($\Delta\nu_{st}$, Table 3) of 1,3,5-phenyl pyrazolines generally range in the 5000-6000 cm^{-1} interval and between 4060-8960 cm^{-1} in our experiments due to substitution. For **4a-g**, the increase in Stokes shift with respect to **4a** follows the order **4b** > **4c** > **4d** according with the electron-donating capability of R (where R = CH₃, OCH₃, and N(CH₃)₂, respectively) due to conjugation of the phenyl fragment that bears R with the main chromophore; for electron-acceptor substituents, the decrease in Stokes shift with respect to **4a** follows the order **4f** > **4e** > **4g** according with the electron-acceptor capability of R (where R = NO₂, Cl, and Br, respectively). Anomalously large Stokes shifts and fluorescence quenching have been explained in different ways (Munoz *et al.*, 2004) including intramolecular hydrogen bonds (Chernova *et al.*, 1973) as in our work.

The aryl fragment at position 5 is a chromophore independent from the main one, fragment a; the aryl fragment has a perpendicular orientation with respect to fragment a and was observed at shorter wavelengths (Blair and Sahyun, 1994) because it is not conjugated with the main chromophore (Figure 1); the hydroxyquinolinic fragment in **4a-g** looks like a shoulder in the absorption curve at ~300-310 nm; for this reason, all the absorption and fluorescence spectra across the **4a-g** series (supporting information) were similar to those of the unsubstituted 1,3,5-triphenylpyrazolines (Doroshenko, 1998).

3.3 Relocation of the electron density

Scheme 3 shows the electron density relocation in fragment a of the triarylpyrazolinic molecule when passing to the excited state; this relocation gives characteristic luminophore properties to pyrazolines and was obtained through quantum calculations by the PM6 method (Stewart, 2007).

In the series **4a-g**, substituents on the benzene ring in position 3 can limit or facilitate such electronic relocation; for example, the dimethylamino group in **4d** produced a shift to shorter wavelength and the nitro group in **4g**, to longer wavelength, both in absorbance and in fluorescence, compared with **4a** (Table 3). The shift to longer wavelength due to substitution increased the absorption from 345 in **4a** to 432 nm in **4g**, and the fluorescence from 444 in **4a** to 567 nm in **4g**.

Scheme 3. Relocation of the electron density in fragment a of triarylpyrazolines

3.4 Fluorescence and intersystem crossing

The low fluorescence of our pyrazolines was atypical of this group of organic compounds. Substitution on the phenyl radical in position 5 of the pyrazolines of the **5a-g** series (fragment b, Scheme 2) did not increase luminescence because fragment b is not conjugated with the main chromophore (Kimura *et al.*, 1977), although there are reports of adverse effects of the substitution at carbon 5 in the pyrazolinic ring on fluorescence; the fluorescence of pyrazolines decreases with π -electron conjugated systems or SO₂X type substituents at position 5 where X is a methyl fluoride group (Krasovitskii *et al.*, 1988). This decrease in fluorescence may be due to competition between fluorescence and intersystem crossing (Svinarev *et al.*, 1990), a radiationless relaxation crossover between electronic states of different multiplicity. Intersystem crossing leads to a radiationless transition in liquid solutions from the triplet state through a "mixed" or "cross" excited state formed with an occupied molecular orbital of one chromophoric fragment and a vacant orbital of another fragment of the pyrazoline (Doroshenko *et al.*, 1997a, b).

A similar behavior occurred for the **4a-g** series: the hydroxyquinolinic electron-acceptor fragment at position 5 in the pyrazolinic cycle quenched fluorescence. Quantum calculations of the excited states of **4a** showed a cross-linked excited state located just a few hundred of cm^{-1} higher than its singlet excited state. An energy difference of 1000 cm^{-1} for similar states would quench fluorescence almost entirely (Doroshenko *et al.*, 1997b). The dissipation of electronic energy without effective emission in the **4a-g** series was the result of processes similar to those described above; for example, the rapid pace of the molecule to the triplet state, with consequent dissipation of energy as heat.

The above cannot explain the very low fluorescent quantum yields of pyrazolines **5a-g**. In this series, the hydroxyquinolinic fragment is part of the main chromophore, which shifts the absorption and fluorescence spectra to the long-wavelength region due to the lengthening of the conjugated chain (Table 3). Substituents introduced in the phenyl group in series **5a-g**, usually did not change the position of the absorption band, and only the nitro group slightly changed the position of the fluorescence band. The possible "cross linked" excited states in this series were located well above the lowest energy excited singlet state and could not take part in the quenching of fluorescence. However, the quantum yields of pyrazolines **5a-g** were as low as in **4a-g**.

3.5 Fluorescence and donor-acceptor interactions

The likely cause of the low fluorescence of derivatives **5a-g** may be the increase of the donor-acceptor interaction of the excited molecules as a result of the electron-acceptor hydroxyquinolinic fragment that attracts the electron cloud in the lower excited singlet state; indeed, according to quantum calculations (PM6 method), the dipole moment of **5a** must increase from $\sim 2 \text{ D}$ in the basal state to $\sim 7 \text{ D}$ in the excited state which would increase the donor-acceptor properties of the excited molecules. Non-rigid molecules with strong intramolecular donor-acceptor interactions often have low quantum yields in solutions of medium to high polarity due to formation of non-fluorescent twisted intramolecular charge transfer states as a result of the formation of dipoles (Rettig, 1986; Lippert *et al.*, 1987). However, the polarity of

solvents such as toluene, used in our experiments, was insufficient to explain the low fluorescence of series **5a-g**.

3.6 Fluorescence and ESIPT reactions

Another possible cause of the low quantum yield of this series of compounds was the photo excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT, Scheme 4) often accompanied by fluorescence quenching (Ameer-Beg *et al.*, 2001). Despite considerable transfer of electron density to the hydroxyquinolinic fragment, the acidity of its hydroxyl group increases in the excited state which favors proton transfer from this group to the hydroxyquinolinic nitrogen in **5a-g**. If the ESIPT reaction rate is fast enough (10^{11} - 10^{12} s^{-1}) (Douhal *et al.*, 1996; Herek *et al.*, 1992), the quantum yield of **5a** would only reach a few tens of percent, which corresponds with the data in Table 3. Estimates on the likely ESIPT reaction product showed that the fluorescence band should be expected in the near IR, between 800-900 nm; the probability of a high intensity emission from **5a-g** in this area is low due to non-emission losses involved in the ESIPT reaction (Doroshenko *et al.*, 2002). Furthermore, the close energy of the excited and basal states in the ESIPT reaction product involves, according to Kasha's rule, a process with a high probability of internal conversion that must exceed the speed of fluorescence emission (Henry and Kasha, 1968).

Scheme 4. Photo excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT)

3.7 Biological activity

All compounds were tested for antifungal activity against a panel of clinically important fungi. Among the compounds tested, **4a** showed the best antifungal activity with minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) lower than those

showed by the chalcones used for its synthesis (Marrugo González *et al.*, 2012).

The MIC and the minimum concentrations needed to kill the fungi (MFC) of **4a**, in µg/mL, were: *Candida albicans* (62.5/ >250); *Candida tropicalis* (125/ >250); *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (62.5/ >250); *Cryptococcus neoformans* (62.5/ >250); *Aspergillus flavus* (125/ >250); *Aspergillus fumigatus* (125/ >250); *Aspergillus niger* (125/ >250); *Microsporum gypseum* (62.5/ 62.5); *Trichophyton rubrum* (62.5/ 125) and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (62.5/ 125). Compound **4a** showed fungicide rather than fungistatic activities against the dermatophytes *M. gypseum*, *T. rubrum* and *T. mentagrophytes*, which give this compound an added value as a candidate for future research. Dermatophytes are responsible for approximately 80–93% of chronic and recurrent dermal infections in human beings which, although not life threatening, are very difficult to eradicate (Weitzman and Summerbell, 1995). As a consequence new structures with antidermatophytic properties are highly welcome.

Additionally, all compounds showed theoretical biological activity, calculated using PASS software (PPS, 2014); for example, all compounds showed activity as substrates of UGT2B12 antibodies, most of them as inhibitors of different enzymes, and some of them as antiprotozoal (Table 4).-

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Supporting Information: ¹H-RMN, IR, and selected UV-vis spectra for compounds of series **4a-g** and **5a-g**

CONCLUSIONS

Eleven pyrazolines were synthesized and characterized by ¹H-NMR, IR, and electronic spectrometry. The probable causes of low fluorescence in our pyrazolines were, in series **4a-g**, the specific intramolecular fluorescence quenching in bicromophores, characteristic of pyrazolinic 5-acceptor substituted systems, and, in series **5a-g**, ESPT reactions and the increasing donor-acceptor intramolecular interaction of their excited molecules. Pyrazoline **4a** showed a promising antifungal activity and all of them showed wide theoretical biological activity.

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Table 1. Physicochemical properties of compounds **4a-g** and **5a-g**. Only compounds **5a**, **5c** and **5e** have been reported in the literature (Marrugo González et al., 2012).

No	Structure	Melting Temperature, °C ^a	Yield, %/hour ^b	N%, Experimental/Theoretical ^c	ν_{OH} , cm ⁻¹ ^d
4a		110	80/5	11.4/11.5	3400
4b		99-100	92/11	11.2/11.1	3410
4c		169-170	90/11	10.5/10.6	3350
4d		111-112	92/10	13.7/13.7	3360

4e		124-125	85/11	10.4/10.5	3395
4f		122-123	84/13	9.4/9.5	3400
4g		140-141	95/6	13.6/13.6	3365
5a		64-65	80/10	11.4/11.5	3410
5b		114-115	85/5	11.2/11.1	3415
5c		124-125	87/5	10.7/10.6	3405
5d		80	83/10	13.6/13.7	3400
5e		113-115	81/6	10.6/10.5	3350
5f		147-148	93/5	9.5/9.5	3395

^a Reported melting temperature: **5a** (218-219 °C); **5c** (151-153 °C); **5e** (80-81 °C) (Marrugo González *et al.*, 2012); melting temperatures reported were higher maybe due to metal ion contamination which forms complexes of higher melting points. ^b Yield after recrystallization from ethanol/ Reaction time. ^c Nitrogen percentage. ^d ν_{OH} : OH stretching band. $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ was 1600 cm^{-1} in KBr

Table 2. ¹H NMR chemical shifts (τ) of compounds **4a-g** and **5a-g**. Chemical shifts of 4-H and H_x signals in **4a** and **5a** differ on average 1.20 and -0.62 ppm, respectively, from those of their **5a-g** isomers, which reflect the spatial location of both heterocycles

No	δ , (ppm) ^a									
	2-H	3-H*	4-H	6-H	7-H	H _A	H _B	H _X	C ₆ H ₄ ^b	CH ₃
4a	8.91	7.63	8.66	7.86	6.72	4.04	4.12	6.04	6.9-7.8	-
4b	8.92	7.51	8.70	7.85	6.70	4.03	4.12	6.01	6.9-7.7	2.31
4c	8.90	7.45	8.70	8.02	6.68	4.00	4.10	5.96	6.9-7.8	3.76
4d	8.90	7.58	8.70	8.07	6.71	3.98	4.06	5.90	6.8-8.0	2.93
4e	8.91	7.50	8.66	7.97	6.73	4.02	4.10	6.07	6.9-7.8	-
4f	8.90	7.43	8.70	7.93	6.73	4.02	4.11	6.06	6.9-7.8	-
4g	8.90	7.49	8.79	7.98	6.70	4.10	4.23	5.90	6.8-7.9	-
5a	8.82	7.83	9.91	8.02	6.78	4.04	4.13	5.42	7.0-7.7	-
5b	8.94	7.83	9.92	7.91	6.78	4.02	4.13	5.38	7.0-7.6	2.23
5c	8.83	7.78	9.89	8.02	6.78	3.99	4.09	5.37	6.8-7.7	3.68
5d	8.90	7.77	9.94	8.20	6.77	3.97	4.06	5.30	7.0-7.7	2.82
5e	8.94	7.8	9.89	7.99	6.74	4.04	4.13	5.45	7.0-7.7	-
5f	8.87	7.73	9.83	7.52	6.69	3.97	4.06	5.39	7.9-7.5	-
5g	8.84	7.81	9.94	8.30	6.77	4.10	4.27	5.65	7.0-7.7	-

^a Spin-spin constants were, in Hz: 2H 0.9-2.4 and 2.4-4.8; 4H 1.2-1.8 and 8.2-8.5; 6H 2.7-8.5; H_A 12.2-14.3 (J_{AX}); H_B 12.2-14.0 (J_{BX}); H_X 5.2-7.0 (J_{XA}) and 11.3-12.7 (J_{XB}). ^b The signals of 3H and protons of the aryl radical of **4a-g**, partially overlapped.

Table 3. Wavelengths of excitation and fluorescence of hydroxyquinolinic derivatives of pyrazolines in toluene. λ : wavelength. ν : frequency. $\Delta\nu_{St}$: Difference between excitation and fluorescence wavelenghts. Φ : quantum yield.

Compound	Excitation		Fluorescence			
	λ , nm	ν , cm^{-1}	λ , nm	ν , cm^{-1}	$\Delta\nu_{St}$, cm^{-1}	Φ
4a	345	29020	444	22500	6520	0.0039
4b	348	28760	480	20840	7920	0.0037
4c	349	28680	488	20480	8200	0.0019
4d	332	30160	472	21200	8960	0.0040
4e	357	28060	455	22000	6060	0.0120
4f	359	27880	490	20420	7460	0.0043
4g	432	23137	567	17640	5497	0.0130
5a	407	24600	535	18700	5900	0.0012
5b	408	24521	579	17280	7241	0.0300
5c	407	24560	492	20340	4220	0.0018
5d	402	24860	489	20440	4420	0.0190
5e	408	24520	489	20460	4060	0.0058
5f	408	24480	578	17280	7200	0.0030
5g	405	24691	552	18100	6591	0.0260

Table 4. Probability of biological theoretical activity calculated with PAAS software for compounds 4a-g and 5a-g.

Biological Activity	Probability, %													
	4a	4b	4c	4d	4e	4f	4g	5a	5b	5c	5d	5e	5f	5g
Dehydro-L-gulonate decarboxylase inhibitor	84	79	-	-	71	71	-	83	77	-	-	-	-	-
UGT2B12 substrate	84	80	81	79	79	79	76	80	75	77	74	75	75	72
Glutathione thiolesterase inhibitor	81	74	-	-	-	-	-	79	72	-	-	-	-	-
Glyceryl-ether monooxygenase inhibitor	78	75	73	73	72	72	-	78	74	72	72	71	71	-
Corticoesteroid side chain inhibitor	78	71	-	-	-	-	-	75	-	-	-	-	-	-
Alkane 1-monooxygenase inhibitor	77	79	-	-	-	-	-	75	77	-	-	-	-	-
Amine dehydrogenase inhibitor	74	-	74	-	-	-	-	70	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gluconate 2- dehydrogenase (acceptor) inhibitor	-	-	71	-	-	-	-	-	-	72	-	-	-	-
(S)-6-hydroxynicotine inhibitor	-	-	-	80	-	-	-	-	-	-	78	-	-	-
Antiprotozoal (amoeba)	-	-	-	70	-	70	-	-	-	-	71	-	71	-